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**BIG DATA
OCEAN**

BigDataOcean

“Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications”

D4.1 BigDataOcean Technology Requirements and User Stories

Workpackage: WP4 – BigDataOcean Service Requirements, User stories, APIs definition, Architecture

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Executive Summary

The current document reports on the results of Task 4.1 and Task 4.2. In particular, it documents 58 BigDataOcean User Stories that have been prepared based on the template "As a <role>, I want <goal/desire>, so that <benefit>", as well as updates and additions on the technology requirements for the BigDataOcean platform. It describes the methodology followed for the requirements elicitation and analysis, as well as the derivation of the user stories. The methodology for the requirements elicitation consists of five phases, namely Preparation, Elicitation, Analysis, Specification, and Validation. This deliverable focuses on the Analysis phase, where the user stories (Task 4.1) and technical requirements (Task 4.1) are consolidated based on raw requirements as identified in Task 2.2 (see Deliverable D2.1). This deliverable hence documents the Technological Requirements of the BigDataOcean platform, as well as indicative technologies that can be used for these requirements. Based on the mentioned technological requirements, as well as on the stakeholders identified in Deliverable 2.1, this deliverable also includes user stories with the aim of refining and eliciting new requirements following a deeper understanding of the project's pilots' expectations. Basically, these user stories are a more concrete way of defining the services that the BigDataOcean platform will provide in order to cater for the requirements of the pilots and potential end users in general. In addition, examples of use case scenarios are discussed in this document.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

This deliverable reports on the progress of BigDataOcean through the activities performed under Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 and provides user stories, as well as the technology requirements for the BigDataOcean platform, as envisioned by the different user groups or stakeholders. The deliverable describes sets of user stories and use case scenarios, deriving mainly from the project's pilot partners. The aim of these user stories and usage scenarios is to indicate all stakeholders' point of view. The reported user stories and usage scenarios are a natural evolution of the requirements identified and reported in WP2 "Stakeholders' Identification, Maritime Data Value Chain Definition and Project Methodology", in particular in deliverable D2.1 "BigDataOcean Analysis Report on Big Data Components Tools and Methodologies". The requirements elicitation methodology consists of five phases, namely Preparation, Elicitation, Analysis, Specification, and Validation. The user stories include a complete high-level description of the expected behaviour of all BigDataOcean sub-systems that are going to be specified and developed in the project. Technological requirements are therefore derived from these user needs.

1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** provides an overall introduction to this report together with positioning this work within the project;
- **Section 2** describes the methodology followed for requirements elicitation and analysis and the derivation of the user stories;
- **Section 3** documents the technological requirements based on the raw requirements gathered during the requirements elicitation phase;
- **Section 4** provides a description of the stakeholders together with related user stories and examples of use case scenarios;
- **Section 5** concludes the document and reports on future steps to follow the deliverable at hand.

1.3 Positioning within the Project

The work reported in this document is part of two tasks (namely T4.1 "Platform Technology Requirements and Integration Components Analysis" and T4.2 "User Stories from Pilots for Big Maritime Data Exploitation") within WP4 "BigDataOcean Service requirements, User stories, APIs definition, Architecture" which covers all the activities related to service requirements, user stories, APIs definition, overall design and architecture of the BigDataOcean platform. More in detail, T4.1 aims at extracting all the technical requirements for the BigDataOcean platform, components and interfaces, while T4.2 is devoted to developing and reporting sets of user stories and usage / use case scenarios, deriving from the project's pilot partners. This work, however, is quite interrelated with the other work packages of the project. It receives as input the early reports of WP2 and WP3

“Cross-Sector Semantics, Analytics and Business Intelligence Algorithms” in order to analyse the findings, concepts and suggestions and extract the technical specifications of the BigDataOcean integrated platform. In particular the input of D2.1 is essential as it provides the raw requirements which are used to derive user stories and technology requirements. Moreover, the review of Big Data tools and technologies landscape described in D2.1 is here further refined and tailored to the needs and solutions envisioned for the BigDataOcean platform. Finally, this deliverable serves as input for all the tasks related to the technical development of the platform and in particular for T4.3 “Components’ and APIs’ Definition and Design” and T4.4 “BigDataOcean Scalable Architecture Design” where the technical requirements are translated into concrete design of the components and a specific platform architecture.

2 Requirements Methodology and Elicitation

The BigDataOcean requirements engineering methodology¹ consists of five phases:

- **Preparation:** this phase includes the stakeholders' characterisation, the identification of the data sources, the definition of the data value chain and the gap identification (i.e., identification of the gaps between the current business strategy and the one expected in BigDataOcean).
- **Elicitation:** this phase is based on the outputs of the Preparation phase, namely the gap identification, and it includes elicitation activities with the pilot partners (e.g., workshops and questionnaires) and the extraction of the raw requirements.
- **Analysis:** the raw requirements produced during the elicitation phase are organised, categorised, and refined in the Analysis phase. The main output of this phase is the consolidation of the user stories that are afterwards validated by the end users. The Analysis phase includes also the specification of the technological needs.
- **Specification:** the user stories defined during the Analysis phase are further refined and prioritised in the Specification phase. After that, the core features and the proof-of-concept specification are defined, which lead to the architecture specification.
- **Validation:** in the last phase of the requirements methodology, a proof-of-concept based on the results of the Specification phase is implemented and its technical and socio-business aspects are evaluated.

The current deliverable focuses on the Analysis phase, namely the consolidation of the user stories (T4.2) and the technical requirements (T4.1) based on the raw requirements identified in T2.2 (see Deliverable D2.1). Figure 1 includes the steps in the applied requirements engineering methodology that are related to the current deliverable. The *User Stories Definition* is based on both the raw requirements that were collected during the Elicitation Phase as well as their refinement and categorisation, which is part of the Analysis Phase. In the Specification Phase, these User Stories will be further refined and prioritised. In addition, the analysis of the User Stories leads to the definition of the technical needs, i.e., technological requirements, which will play an important role in the architecture specification of BigDataOcean.

¹ Adapted from the OSMOSE requirements Methodology (used in the FP7 OSMOSE project - 610905) (OSMOSE Project, 2014) and in the IEEE Standard.

Figure 1: BigDataOcean Requirements Engineering Methodology - Focus on the Analysis Phase

3 Technological Requirements

In this section, the technological requirements of BigDataOcean platform are documented, based on the raw requirements gathered during the Elicitation phase. Moreover, this deliverable documents the Big Data tools and technologies landscape that was analysed in Deliverable D2.1. In particular, state-of-the-art tools and technologies were evaluated with regard to the needs of the various users and stakeholders of the BigDataOcean platform. The topics that BigDataOcean targets include:

1. *Data Collection* (Technical Interoperability, Event Detection, Data Linking and Aggregation, Multilingual Translation, Data Extraction, Identification, and Integration, Data Access Control, Privacy, and Security);
2. *Data Management* (Semantic Interoperability, Semantic Enrichment, Curation and Cleaning, Data Storage, Partitioning, and Distribution, Query Processing);
3. *Data Analytics* (Data Mining, Simulation and Forecasting, Machine Learning);
4. *Data Visualisation*.

This deliverable provides a discussion on the technological requirements with respect to the stage in the BigDataOcean Data Value Chain they are related to. In Section 3.1, an introduction on BigDataOcean Data Value Chain is provided, along with an example based on one of the project pilots. After that, Section 3.2 reports on the tools and technologies that will be used in BigDataOcean.

3.1 BigDataOcean Data Value Chains

Figure 2 illustrates the steps that compose the maritime data value chain to be implemented in Big maritime data applications.

Figure 2: The BigDataOcean Data Value Chain

First, during data acquisition, diverse methods are required to collect raw maritime data gathered from different devices and instruments, and reported in various formats. Once maritime data is collected, diverse data analytic methods are necessary to determine accuracy and data integration problems. During data curation, quality issues are assessed, and data is also integrated. Then, different methods for data compression, indexing, and accessing are required to efficiently store maritime-related data. As a next step, data processing and analytics are necessary to identify patterns and predict relations across maritime data, thus allowing for value enhancing. Moreover, during all the steps of the data value chain, privacy issues, data protection, and security risks should be addressed. Additionally, tools for effective utilisation, analysis, and visualisation of maritime data need to be available; these tools need to be able to support both stream and heterogeneous data. Finally, data governance and provenance both have to be taken into account in every step of the data value chain.

Figure 3: Example of a Data Value Chain in BigDataOcean

Figure 3 illustrates an exemplary Data Value Chain based on the requirements of Big Data Ocean Pilot 3 - Maritime Security and Anomaly Detection. Vessel tracking data is collected, e.g., in a database, in the first step. Vessels in the Aegean Sea are curated and filtered, as well as data related to these vessels in the second step (i.e., Data Analysis). Then, vessels are classified by type and are persisted in a database. A service for vessel monitoring is finally deployed to fulfil the Data Usage step.

3.2 Requirements Fulfilment of Technical Needs

Table 1 includes the list of technology requirements in the BDO Data Value Chain as well as indicative technologies in each category.

Table 1: BigDataOcean Technology Requirements

Step in BigDataOcean Data Value Chain	Technology Requirements
Data Acquisition	<p>DAC-TR-1: The system should be able to connect and acquire data from sensors and IoT devices of different manufactures in real-time or intervals.</p> <p>DAC-TR-2: The system should be able to obtain data from AIS receivers, transponders or base stations.</p> <p>DAC-TR-3: The system should be able to acquire data from large and popular oceanographic databases including Copernicus through APIs.</p> <p>DAC-TR-4: The system should be able to upload big data datasets on BigDataOcean infrastructure.</p> <p>DAC-TR-5: The system should be able to link big data sources to BigDataOcean Infrastructure.</p> <p><i>Indicative technologies for data harvesting are related to the usage of RESTful JSON APIs, MOTU REST API²</i></p>
Data Analysis	<p>DAN-TR-1: The system should be able to perform big data analytic algorithms on the data stored / linked in the</p>

² <http://marine.copernicus.eu/faq/can-i-automate-downloads-of-cmems-products/>

	<p>BigDataOcean platform including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics.</p> <p>DAN-TR-2: The system should be able to save results of the analyses as datasets that can be further analysed with other algorithms.</p> <p>DAN-TR-3: The data analysis framework should be performed on a scalable cluster-computing framework, programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance.</p> <p>DAN-TR-4: The BDO analytics should have the capability to perform streaming analytics.</p> <p><i>Indicative technologies for big data analytics are: Apache SPARK (with MLib and R), Apache Storm, and DataTorrent RTS. Moreover, analytic software tools to be considered in this area are: Weka, Rapidminer, R, Orange, IBM SPSS, SAS, STATISTICA, Apache Mahout.</i></p>
<p>Data Curation</p>	<p>DC-TR-1: The system should be able to cleanse the datasets (e.g. remove duplicates, inconsistent values, identify outliers, values with wrong types).</p> <p>DC-TR-2: The system should be able to curate large scale (big data) datasets in a timely and efficient manner.</p> <p>DC-TR-3: The system should be able to store the processes followed for the data curation.</p> <p>DC-TR-4: The system should allow for efficient transformation of data: converting values to other formats, normalising and de-normalising.</p> <p>DC-TR-5: The system should be able to program the semantic curation / reconciliation of datasets.</p> <p>DC-TR-6: The data curation tools can be used offline at the client side.</p> <p><i>Indicative technologies for data curation include: OpenRefine, KARMA, DataWrangler and DataCleaner.</i></p>
<p>Data Storage</p>	<p>DS-TR-1: The system should be able to store and manage large datasets (big data).</p> <p>DS-TR-2: Setup of different data storage environments should be allowed in parallel in order to accommodate different storage needs (Relational Databases, NoSQL, TripleStores).</p> <p>DS-TR-3: The system should have high degree of scalability.</p> <p>DS-TR-4: The system should allow for replication and high availability with no single point of failure.</p> <p>DS-TR-5: The system should support distributed storage and</p>

	<p>auto-sharing.</p> <p>DS-TR-6: The system should offer native security and encryption mechanisms.</p> <p>DS-TR-7: The system should have a direct pipeline with the chosen cluster computing framework and analytics engine.</p> <p><i>Indicative technologies for data storage include: MongoDB, Cassandra, HBase, PostgreSQL, VoltDB, BlazeGraph, Apache Accumulo, TripleStores such as Virtuoso.</i></p>
Data Usage	<p>DU-TR-1: The system should be able to perform simple and advanced queries over the stored big data.</p> <p>DU-TR-2: The system should be able to visualize stored and real-time data using common chart types (bar chart, line chart, pie chart, etc.).</p> <p>DU-TR-3: The visualisations should be linked to the queries performed over the data.</p> <p>DU-TR-4: The system should be able to visualise statistics, real-time data and spatial datasets.</p> <p>DU-TR-5: The system should be able to create and save static and dynamic dashboards and reports.</p> <p>DU-TR-6: The system should be able to export data and results of visualisations through APIs.</p> <p><i>Indicative technologies of data usage include: LinDA Query Designer, Tableau, DataWatch, Lumify, ZoomData, D3.js, AmCharts, Spagobi.</i></p>

A Data Value Chain in BigDataOcean as the one depicted in Figure 3, can be implemented as a pipeline of the BigDataEurope platform³. This platform will combine data of different velocity, variety and volume under an inter-linked, trusted, multilingual engine to produce a big-data repository of value and veracity back to the participants and local communities. Big data components required to implement each of the steps of a data value chain, e.g., a semantic data lake or a data analytics tool, will be integrated in the pipeline. Components will be either locally stored in the BigDataOcean development machines, or accessible via Web services. To scale up to the heterogeneous nature of the BigDataOcean datasets, i.e., volume, velocity, and variety, components like Apache Spark and Hadoop HDFS can be integrated in the pipeline too.

³ <https://www.big-data-europe.eu/pipeline-2/>

4 User Stories

4.1 Stakeholders

Whilst BigDataOcean targets the maritime sector as an application domain, the project still caters for a number of different stakeholders, as defined in Deliverable 2.1. In fact, the various stakeholders who can benefit from the outcome of this project are identified through four pilots, as shown in Figure 4. This section provides a short overview of the pilots and indicative respective stakeholders, in order for this deliverable to be self-contained.

Figure 4: Overview of Indicative Stakeholders of each Pilot in BigDataOcean

4.1.1 Pilot 1: Fault Prediction and Proactive Maintenance

This pilot concerns the operational tools that are currently being used as part of the process that provides essential information for properly handling fault prediction and proactive maintenance on various types of vessels. Through this pilot, data from a number of sensors that constantly collect operational and performance data on every critical aspect (e.g. engines' strain, emissions) will be used to formulate a knowledge base that each owner and/or operator exploits towards the effort of being proactive rather than reactive, towards controlling unpredicted damages and/or mechanical failures, in order to avoid unnecessary costs.

- **Stakeholder 1: Ship Owners**

Ship owners include the owner of a merchant vessel (commercial ship) and are involved in the shipping industry. A ship owner equips and exploits a ship, usually for delivering cargo at a certain freight rate, either as a per freight rate (given price for the transport of a certain cargo between two given ports) or based on hire (a rate per day). Ship owners typically hire a licensed crew and captain rather than take charge of the vessel in person.

- **Stakeholder 2: Maritime Equipment Constructors**

Maritime equipment constructors are manufacturers of the machinery and equipment of the ships that also provide equipment maintenance plans and agreements with ship owners and managers marine equipment, concerning products such as machine engines, navigation systems, electrical and electronics systems, as well as metal products and materials.

4.1.2 Pilot 2: Mare Protection

This pilot is concerned with enabling the proper handling of pollution accidents in the marine environment through the use of tools as part of a Decision Support System. Oil spills, for example, require crucial planning and preparing of effective response strategies. Oil spill models rely on the ability to predict meteo-marine conditions of the sea through the use of cross-sectorial data including atmospheric, wave and hydrodynamic numerical models. Integrating and combining the information on the location, rate, nature, and characteristics of an oil spill, the derived forecasted fields are used to provide in advance some knowledge on the fate and track that the oil slick will follow in time.

- **Stakeholder 3: Emergency Response Companies**

Emergency response companies that are responsible to provide environmental protection services and quickly respond to oil spill incidents. The available services include oil and chemical spill response, hazardous waste management, protection and preparedness for ports and installations, management of distressed cargo, design & production of marine equipment and tank cleaning.

- **Stakeholder 4: National Entities**

Research and Educational Units, or public and governmental entities, under the supervision of the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change. These entities provide support on marine environment protection and marine safety, while also promoting maritime transport research and development.

- **Stakeholder 5: Non-Governmental Organisation**

NGOs cooperate with local communities and authorities to develop and apply pilot management and conservation projects aimed at protecting habitats and species of the Greek Seas and the north-eastern Mediterranean. Additionally, they work directly to stop destructive human behaviour, such as illegal fishing practices, explosions at sea, waste dumping, maritime pollution, erosive overgrazing and other threats to biodiversity.

- **Stakeholder 6: Marine Research Institute**

Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR) is a governmental research organisation operating under the supervision of the Ministry of Education, Research and Religious Affairs of Greece.

4.1.3 Pilot 3: Maritime Security and Anomaly Detection

This pilot concerns Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA), which is the effective understanding of activities, events, and threats in the maritime environment that could impact global safety, security, economic activity, or the environment. The major challenge to be addressed in this pilot is developing the ability to identify patterns within vast amounts of data, fused from various sources, so as to act proactively and minimise the impact of possible threats. This pilot will perform behaviour and pattern analysis of enhanced trajectories/vessel profiles exploiting vessel movement information (e.g. counts

of turns, turn around, halts, speed ups in a given time window, etc.) and assess the risks to accurately predict maritime security or movement anomaly incidents.

- **Stakeholder 7: Port Authorities**

Ports are public business entities with responsibility of operating ports and other transport infrastructures. Services include execution of the port policies of the government, general coordination with the different bodies of the General State Administration, training, promotion of research and technological development in matters related to the economy, management, logistics and port engineering and other related to the activity that takes place in ports. In some states a single entity is responsible for coordinating and controlling the efficiency of a whole port system and not only a single port.

- **Stakeholder 8: Ocean Observatories**

Ocean observatories provide oceanographic data, modelling services and new technologies to support oceanography and marine and coastal research towards integrated and science based coastal and ocean management.

- **Stakeholder 9: Port/Cargo Community Systems**

Port/Cargo community systems are complex information systems that optimise logistics processes especially in international trade hub like ports and airports by facilitating and streamlining data flows between international trade players using our information systems for smoother, more traceable and more competitive transactions.

- **Stakeholder 10: Transport and Logistics**

Software technology providers have been developing solutions for the Maritime Industry related to Maritime Security, Transport Logistics, etc.

- **Stakeholder 11: Harbour Pilots and Maritime Consultants**

Harbour Pilots are primarily concerned with directing the movement of vessels in a harbour environment from an on-board position.

4.1.4 Pilot 4: Wave Power as the Next Clean Energy Source

Wave power and tidal power both have the potential of contributing extensively to the production of clean energy. In order to move on from the greenhouse gas-generating fossil fuels, many are now looking toward the untapped resources of our oceans as a sustainable source of energy. Examples include offshore wind energy, ocean thermal energy conversion, tidal energy, wave energy, and ocean current energy. While tapping into these clean sources for generating energy is a good idea, the wave energy industry is still in its infancy and there are a number of technological challenges that act as a barrier to further development. Furthermore it is necessary to ensure that marine life is protected. It is therefore vital to accurately aggregate data in order to effectively predict the best locations, the expected energy production, and the negative impacts on the production equipment.

- **Stakeholder 12: Hydrographical Centre**

The hydrographical centre is normally a public organisation that carries out activities in the maintenance of official nautical cartography and related marine sciences (oceanography, chemistry and pollution, processing and data integration).

- **Stakeholder 13: Offshore Renewables Service Provider**

This type of provider is a consulting organisation with a strong R&D background. Its activity is targeting services for offshore sectors such as wave and wind energy as well as aquaculture. Services include marine studies of coast characterisation based on numerical models, using raw data (provided by another entity).

- **Stakeholder 14: Zone Concessionaire**

Entity with the concession for the exploitation of a certain geographical region. In the case of pilot 4, it is targeting regions for the production of energy of the waves, with the purpose of implanting the infrastructures and connection to the public energy network.

- **Stakeholder 15: Energy Producer**

This type of entity is responsible for the installation of the power converters and for the energy production process management.

4.2 BigDataOcean User Stories

User stories provide a high-level definition of a requirement that describes in an informal language the goal and benefit of a feature from a specific perspective, i.e., for a specific user role. The current section documents 58 User Stories that have been written based on the template "As a <role>, I want <goal/desire>, so that <benefit>". These User Stories are based on the raw requirements collected and described in deliverable D2.1.

Table 2 provides an overview of the user stories, as extracted from the raw requirements identified from the pilots. This deliverable refines and also elicits new requirements following a deeper understanding of the pilots. These are then derived in the User Stories. In the Table below it is possible to follow the evolution from the raw requirement until the user story, as well as the mapping between the new requirements and the requirements described in deliverable D2.1. These user stories are a more concrete way of defining the services that the BigDataOcean platform will provide, in order to cater for the requirements of the stakeholders.

Table 2: BigDataOcean User Stories

ID	BigDataOcean To-BE	Related BigDataOcean Raw Requirements (D2.1)	User Story (As a <role>, I want <goal/desire>, so that <benefit>)
US-1	BigDataOcean platform should be able to correlate data from multiple data sources	DC-04	As a data analyst, I want the BigDataOcean platform to have semantic services that allow to access correlated data, so that potentially new insights can be discovered.
US-2	BigDataOcean platform should have user accounts management		As an administrator, I want to be able to create an account to save my searches and preferences in the system, so that I could save my work for later reuse and manage its

			privacy levels.
US-3	BigDataOcean platform should allow browsing and search for datasets	DA-01, DA-02, DA-03, DA-04, DA-05	As a data consumer, I want to be able to search for specific datasets, based on various criteria, or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily and efficiently find relevant data to use.
US-4	BigDataOcean platform should allow the exploration of datasets (basic and advanced view)	DA-01, DA-02, DA-03, DA-04, DA-05	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to explore the main properties of the available datasets or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily find relevant data for my requirements.
US-5	BigDataOcean platform should allow free downloading or purchasing of some datasets/services		As a data consumer, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to make available free downloading and purchasing of available datasets, so that diverse types of dataset access can be offered by the BigDataOcean platform.
US-6	BigDataOcean platform should allow users to view quality metrics of datasets	DC-02	As a data consumer, I would like to view different quality metrics of the datasets, so that I can select the most appropriate data to use for my use case.
US-7	BigDataOcean platform should offer a set of analytics and services on one or multiple datasets	DA-08, DA-09, DC-07	As a data analyst, I would need analytics tools and services that can run on one or multiple datasets, so that I would be able to identify any abnormalities and also extract new knowledge.
US-8	BigDataOcean platform should offer a set of online tools for monitoring or reporting in particular use cases	DC-04, DC-05	As a data consumer, I would like to use online tools for monitoring or reporting, so that I can generate relevant reports.
US-9	BigDataOcean platform should allow users to create their own queries over datasets	DP-01	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to create specific queries, so that I could obtain more relevant answers to reflect my requirements.

US-10	BigDataOcean platform should allow users to build their own services	DP-02	As a service developer, I would like to be able to build my own services through an easy-to-use web interface that allows for mashups and configurations of existing reusable services.
US-11	BigDataOcean platform should allow users to configure their own services	DP-02	As a service consumer, I would like to be able to configure and personalise existing services offered by the platform. This should be possible with an easy-to-use web interface that allows setting and tuning of variables and parameters of different services in order to better fit my requirements for data consumption.
US-12	BigDataOcean platform should allow users to register their own requests for datasets which are currently not integrated in the platform		As a data provider, I would like to be able to describe and register specific datasets, so that I could make available metadata about datasets even if they are not integrated in the platform.
US-13	BigDataOcean platform should be able to browse through users' datasets requests		As a data manager, I would like to be able to explore the dataset requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability, storage, and management of datasets can be better planned.
US-14	BigDataOcean platform should be able to browse through users' services requests		As a data manager, I would like to be able to explore the service requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability and management of services can be better planned.
US-15	BigDataOcean platform should be able to transform data into different formats	DC-03, DC-01	As a data manager, I would like to be able to explore the data transformation requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that data transformation and curation of available datasets can be better planned.
US-16	BigDataOcean platform should be able to handle multi-format datasets	DA-07	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to use datasets with heterogeneous formats, so that I would not be limited to only consume datasets of only a specific format.

US-17	BigDataOcean platform should enable the use of standards to represent data	DA-10	As a data manager, I would like to be able to manage the datasets to be represented using existing standards, so that it would be easier to consume them in the consequent stages of the data life cycle.
US-18	BigDataOcean platform should provide transformation services to enable format independency	DC-03	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to transform datasets, so that they can be used independently of their original format.
US-19	BigDataOcean platform should provide visualisation services	DA-15	As a data analyst, I would like to have visualisation services, so that I can visually analyse existing datasets.
US-20	BigDataOcean platform should provide recommendations on possibly relevant data to the user	DC-07	As a data consumer, I would like to receive recommendations about datasets, so that the BigDataOcean platform effectively helps me fulfil my information requirements.
US-21	BigDataOcean platform should enable criteria dependent outputs	DC-06, DP-01	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to affect the results of services depending on varying priorities, so that the results reflect my needs better.
US-22	BigDataOcean platform should allow downloading of generated reports	DA-14, DA-16	As a data manager, I would like to download the generated reports produced by the system, so that I can self-archive them.
US-23	BigDataOcean platform should allow downloading results of queries and other analysis processes	DC-02, DC-05	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to download the generated results of my queries or my services, so that I can store or further process them.
US-24	BigDataOcean platform should allow the creation of dashboards to visualise and analyse data	DC-02	As a data analyst, I would like to be able to create my own dashboards that will visualise existing data, so that I can analyse and compare different data sources.
US-25	BigDataOcean Platform should be able to ensure data persistence	DS-01	As a user, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data persistence so that I can be confident that my own data, and the data used by my processes/services, is always available and it will be for long time in the future.

US-26	BigDataOcean Platform should be able to ensure data availability	DS-02	As a manager, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data availability, so that data is available for data consumers at a required level of performance during normal or extraordinary operation.
US-27	Platform should be able to ensure data consistency	DS-03	As a data consumer, I want the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data consistency, so that data storage is always conducted according to specific rules, and it is therefore easier to consume the required data.
US-28	BigDataOcean should ensure availability of vessels' position data and support visualisation	DC-02	As a data consumer, I want to find and use vessels' positioning information data, so that I can visualise them on a map for an easily digestible overview.
US-29	BigDataOcean should ensure availability of weather historical data and support data correlation	DA-15	As a data analyst, I want to find and use credible weather historical data, so that I can correlate them with my company's events' registry and come up with possible insights and/or patterns.
US-30	BigDataOcean should ensure service availability		As a service consumer, I want to find and consume the "vessels' certified path" service, so that I can check whether a location for installing offshore equipment is safe.

As opposed to the user stories in the above Table 2, in the following Table 3 an overview of user stories as extracted from the stakeholders' descriptions is provided. Therefore, the following user stories are more relevant to the specific pilots' needs. The relevant pilots are indicated in the rightmost column of the table.

Table 3: User Stories specific to BigDataOcean pilots

ID	BigDataOcean To-BE	User Story (As a <role>, I want <goal/desire>, so that <benefit>)	Pilot
US-31	BigDataOcean platform should be able to use historical data on incidents, casualties, inspections' results	As a user (ship owner), I would like to be able to manage and access historical data on vessel inspections, incidents, and casualties, so that analytics components can be developed for the prediction of potential new incidents.	1

US-32	BigDataOcean platform should provide a service to access reports about pollution of certain oceanographic areas.	As a user (emergency response company), I would like to access reports about the pollution of oceanographic areas, so that I could identify concentration of chemicals, particles, industrial, agricultural, and residential waste in the sea.	2
US-33	The system should provide a service to access Aeronautical Information System data	As a user (national entity), I would like to access Aeronautical Information Systems, so that conditions of international air navigation can be collected and analysed.	2
US-34	BigDataOcean platform should provide service for proactive maintenance and fault prediction	As a user (ship owner), I would like to be able to use a proactive maintenance and fault prediction service, so that I can have better maintenance and fault prediction of the ship machinery and equipment.	1
US-35	BigDataOcean platform should provide notification and alerts to visualise maintenance schedule and incidents	As a user (ship owner), I would like to be able to visualise all maintenance schedules and incidents related to a ship, so that I can have better maintenance and fault prediction of the ship machinery and equipment.	1
US-36	BigDataOcean platform should provide service for visual analytics about the endurance, incidents and faults of specific equipment over different ships	As a user (maritime equipment constructor), I would like to have a service providing visual analytics about the endurance, incidents, and faults of specific equipment over different ships, so that I can automatically gather insights and intelligence about the equipment incidents, maximum tolerance, capabilities, and faults, and thus, improve my maintenance plans.	1
US-37	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool for descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to vessels' movement tracking.	As a user (emergency response company, non-governmental organisation), I would like to have access to descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics about vessels' movement tracking, so that I can enhance efficiency in emergency response for the protection and clean-up of the industrial and marine environment and decrease mobilisation costs.	2

US-38	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool to visualise the Oil Spill dispersion according to the forecasting model that will be used by the pilot 2.	As a user (emergency response company, national entity, non-governmental organisation, marine research institute), I would like to be able to visualise Oil Spill dispersion, so that I can improve precision of prediction, enhance efficiency in emergency response for the protection and clean-up of the industrial and marine environment, and decrease mobilisation costs.	2
US-39	BigDataOcean platform should provide tool to provide analytics regarding the marine ecosystems	As a user (national entity), I would like to have analytics over marine ecosystems, so that I can increase protection and conservation of National and European biotopes, protection and clean-up of the industrial and marine environment, and decrease mobilisation costs.	2
US-40	BigDataOcean platform should provide tool to monitor/visualise areas with fisheries activity	As a user (national entity, non-governmental organisation), I would like to monitor areas with fisheries activity, so that I can increase protection and conservation of National and European seas and enhance protection and clean-up of the industrial and marine environment and impede illegal fishing activities.	2
US-41	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool for descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to the status of vessels calling ports	As a user (port authority), I would like to have descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to the vessels calling ports, so that I can improve the efficiency of the coordination and controlling of the port systems.	3
US-42	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool to visualise the events related to the vessels' calling ports such as "on-schedule", "delayed", "arrived", etc.	As a user (port authority), I would like to visualise events related to the vessels' calling ports such as "on-schedule", "delayed", "arrived", etc., so that I can increase efficiency of the coordination and controlling of the port systems.	3

US-43	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool for descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to vessels' movement tracking	As a user (ocean observatory), I would like to have descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to the vessel's' movement tracking, so that I can monitor and manage the collision risk with ocean gliders, environmental risk, fishing identification, underwater noise, and marine spatial planning.	3
US-44	BigDataOcean platform should provide a visualisation tool to enable information exchange and in-time accurate alerts on movement anomalies of vessels	As a user (ocean observatory), I would like to visualise and enable information exchange and in-time accurate alerts on movement anomalies of vessels, so that I can monitor and manage the collision risk with ocean gliders, environmental risk, fishing identification, underwater noise, and marine spatial planning.	3
US-45	BigDataOcean platform should provide an API that will deliver data analytics related to vessels' movement tracking in cases of anomaly detection to the user	As a user (port/cargo community system), I would like to use an API which will deliver data analytics related to the vessel's' movement tracking in cases of anomaly detection, so that I can optimise logistics processes for resilient supply chain.	3
US-46	BigDataOcean platform should provide an API that delivers notification alerts related to vessel position, weather/event/incidents	As a user (transport and logistics company), I would like to use an API which will deliver notification alerts related to vessel position, weather/events/incidents, so that I can improve software solutions for maritime security and transport logistics.	3
US-47	BigDataOcean platform should provide ship-to-ship and ship-to-shore monitoring services	As a user (harbour pilot and maritime consultant), I would like to have ship-to-ship and ship-to-shore monitoring services, so that I can allow a better controlling of the movement of a vessel, targeting autonomous operation in the future.	3

US-48	BigDataOcean platform should provide a visualisation tool that enables information exchange and in-time accurate alerts on movement anomalies of vessels	As a user (harbour pilot and maritime consultant), I would like to use a visualisation tool that will enable information exchange and in-time accurate alerts on movement anomalies of vessels, so that I can identify alerts and direct the movement of vessels efficiently.	3
US-49	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool to improve the quality of the acquiring, processing and integrating of the data	As a user (hydrographic centre), I would like to have a tool for acquiring, processing, and integrating data related to equipment in the sea, so that I can achieve better quality and maintenance of the data.	4
US-50	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool to predict the maintenance of the equipment	As a user (hydrographic centre), I would like to have a tool to predict the maintenance of equipment, so that I can reduce equipment degradation.	4
US-51	BigDataOcean platform should have a tool to provide more and new raw data to support the assessment of the coast	As a user (offshore renewable service provider), I would like to use a tool that will provide more and new raw data to support the assessment of the coast, so that I can improve offshore renewable energy site selection and resource assessment.	4
US-52	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool to visualise the coast with the marine data, positions of the buoys and current plant location	As a user (offshore renewable service provider), I would like to use a tool to visualise the coast with the marine data, positions of the buoys and current plant location, so that I can improve offshore renewable energy site selection and resource assessment.	4
US-53	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool to forecast the best positions to add new plant location (e.g. wave and wind)	As a user (offshore renewable service provider, zone concessionaire, energy producer), I would like to have a tool to forecast the best positions to add new plant locations, so that I can improve my services regarding site planning.	4

US-54	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool to predict equipment maintenance needs	As a user (offshore renewable service provider, zone concessionaire), I would like to have a tool to predict equipment maintenance needs, so that I can decrease equipment maintenance costs.	4
US-55	BigDataOcean platform should provide a tool to predict the energy production for selective maritime zones	As a user (zone concessionaire), I would like to have a tool to predict the energy production for selective maritime zones, so that I can improve offshore renewable energy site selection.	4
US-56	BigDataOcean platform should provide site planning features	As a user (energy producer), I would like to have site planning features, so that I can enhance energy production.	4

4.3 Example Use Case Representations

Based on the identified stakeholders within this project, as well as the identified requirements and user stories, this section identifies a number of sample use cases that portray, in a more abstract manner, how BigDataOcean aims to cater for the identified requirements. Table 4 presents examples of services with respect to the expected inputs and outputs that will be part of the different modules (e.g., Query Processing, Analytics, etc.) of the BigDataOcean platform. These use case scenarios may be related to one or more of the four pilots in the project.

Table 4: Exemplary BigDataOcean Scenarios

Pilot	Module	Input	Output
3	Query Processing	Vessels, Ports, Timetables	Which <type of vessel> have arrived at the <port> in this <period of time>?
2, 4	Query Processing	Vessels, Buoys, Buoy Observations	Which <wave height, dominant wave period, average wave period> have been measured by <buoy> in this <period of time>?
1, 2, 3, 4	Query Processing	Sensor, Weather Observations	Which <temperature, wind speed, wind direction, air pressure> have been measured by <sensor> in this <period of time>?
1	Query Processing	Vessels, Sensors, Observations, Systems, System	Which <temperature, pressure, vibration, sensor> have been measured by sensor of a <system> in a vessel <vesselID> in this <period of time>?

2	Analytics	Weather Observation, Buoy Observations, Sea Observations	How is <oil dispersion> under atmospheric conditions <temperature, wind speed, wind direction, air pressure> sea conditions <wave height, dominant wave period, average wave period, wave main direction> oceanographic conditions <surface temperature, salinity>?
3	Analytics and Visualisation	Incidents, Weather Observation, Buoy Observations, Vessel Routes	Which <anomalous vessel trajectories> in the sea <sea coordinates> in this <period of time>?
1	Analytics and Visualisation	Vessels, System Observations, Weather Observation, Buoy Observations, Maintenance Scheduler	Which <equipment maintenance > in the vessel <vessel> in the system <system> in this <period of time>?
1	Analytics	Incidents, Weather Observation, Vessels, Maintenance Scheduler, Engine Data	Which <maintenance schedule> in the vessel <vessel> in this <period of time>?
3	Analytics	Incidents, Weather Observation, Vessels, Vessel Routes	Which <incident prediction> in the vessel <vessel> in this <period of time>?

These scenarios cater for the execution of data management tasks on-demand. Data management tasks include semantic enrichment, and data curation and integration. The BigDataOcean query processing engine executes queries against the data lake and fires the data management tasks required to ensure that query answers are semantically enriched.

Figure 4 illustrates a user story implemented at the data management level in the BigDataOcean platform. Users request to know the tank vessels that have arrived in a given port, e.g., the port of Piraeus, in a time period. A SPARQL query represents this request, and the BigDataOcean query processing engine returns the required information containing the specific vessels that arrived in the port of Piraeus. The BigDataOcean query processing engine ensures that only the data that is required to evaluate the query is semantified with the BigDataOcean vocabulary, while execution time is not negatively affected. On-demand semantic enrichment avoids that large volumes of data irrelevant for a user story are semantically described. Thus, data storage is more efficiently utilised as compared to an approach where all the data is semantically described independently. The BigDataOcean platform also offers different big data analytics and visualisation methods; however, it

also allows for the integration of new big data methods. Data required during data analytics and visualisation is collected from the data lake using the BigDataOcean query engine, therefore as explained above, semantic enrichment of the required data is conducted on-demand. Figure 5 presents user stories for data analytics and visualisation.

Figure 5: Example of Query Processing in BigDataOcean: a sample SPARQL query to select the tanker vessels that have arrived into the port of Piraeus for a specific time period.

Figure 5a presents two prediction user stories: (i) Incidents that may occur to the BigDataOcean vessels; (ii) maintenance schedules the BigDataOcean vessels should follow. In both prediction user stories, data about incidents, vessels, weather observations, ship engines, and maintenance observations is accessed from the data lake by executing the corresponding SPARQL queries, and the BigDataOcean vocabulary is used to semantically describe the collected data. Similarly, Figure 5b illustrates three analytics and visualisation user stories: (i) Impact on maritime activities on the maritime life; (ii) equipment maintenance; and (iii) anomalous vessel trajectories. To evaluate these three user stories, buoys and environmental, wave, and tide observations are collected from the data lake, as well as vessels and their trajectories. The BigDataOcean query processing engine is utilised to access the required data and to perform semantic enrichment, curation, and integration. Here, the BigDataOcean vocabulary (bdo) is used to semantically enrich and link data about incidents, maintenance schedules, engines, vessels, trajectories, and observations on-demand. Then, data analytics methods mine this integrated dataset to identify both unknown relations among vessels and equipment maintenance, and vessels and anomalous trajectories. Additionally, community detection algorithms classify oceanographic species according to the potential to be impacted by the evaluated maritime activities. The identified discoveries are passed to the visualisation components to explore the predicted associations and patterns.

Figure 6: Example of Data Analytics in BigDataOcean. (a) Data processing and analytics methods are used to identify incidents and maintenance schedules of vessels in the data lake. (b) Visualisation methods are implemented on top of the data lake to visualise the impact on maritime life, equipment maintenance, and anomaly detection.

5 Conclusions and Future Steps

Based on a five-steps requirements' engineering methodology (namely Preparation, Elicitation, Analysis, Specification and Validation), and focusing mainly on the Analysis step, the deliverable at hand consolidates the BigDataOcean user stories and updates and enriches the technical requirements, receiving as main input the raw requirements reported in the context of deliverable D2.1.

A concrete set of 28 technology requirements is, thus, reported and mapped with the BigDataOcean data value chain, in order to showcase the connection between them, while indicative technologies for each mapping are proposed as well.

Following the aforementioned work, in the context of the current deliverable 58 BigDataOcean User Stories that have been prepared based on the template "As a <role>, I want <goal/desire>, so that <benefit>" are reported. A quick recap of the BigDataOcean pilots and of the relevant stakeholders' categories that are implied through them, is also realised, in order to come up with a number of sample use cases that portray, in a more abstract manner, how BigDataOcean aims to cater for the previously identified requirements.

The work reported in the deliverable at hand provides a high-level description of the expected functionalities and behaviour of all BigDataOcean sub-systems and is going to be fed to the design and development tasks of the project, in order to guide the relevant activities.

Annex I: References

- [1] OSMOSE Project. (2014). D2.11 First User Scenarios & Business Expectations. Retrieved from
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